

THE ROLE OF NEGOTIATION SKILLS IN CAREER DEVELOPMENT AND ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS: A STUDY OF SRI LANKA STATE UNIVERSITIES

KMCU. Champika

Senior Assistant Registrar, Uva Wellassa University, Sri Lanka

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14028883>

Abstract. *In this research study emphasis is given to identifying the role which negotiation skill plays in employment advancement and organizational performance of the state universities in Sri Lanka. Based on both qualitative and quantitative research, the paper examines the issue of the relation between negotiation skills as well as the processes of the personal and professional development of the academic and administrative staff and organizational performance of the state universities. The objectives of the study are to: establish the bargaining skills essential for promotion and organization effectiveness; assess career advancement and negotiation competency development needs and opportunities in the designated organizations to support improved negotiation training. It was also found out from the results that the level of negotiations applied has a positive impact on the aspects of job satisfaction, chances of being promoted and efficient use of resources. The study has implications on the process of policy making within state university organizations to moderate the perceived organizational climate and access to career opportunities.*

Keywords: *negotiation skills, Career development, Organizational effectiveness, Sri Lanka State Universities, Academic management, Resource allocation.*

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Consequently, in today's modern universities, primarily in the state system, negotiation occupies an important place as a factor in staff development and organizational functioning of a higher education establishment. Negotiation is an important way of handling disputes, acquiring research grants, balancing work loads, and career progression in Sri Lanka's state universities most of which are poorly endowed. Consequently, the purpose of this paper is to examine the role of negotiations in career advancement and organizational success, within the Sri Lankan state universities environment.

More and more it is apparent that negotiation aptitudes are essential in rising up the career ladder, as well as in the efficiency and productivity of organizations. Business negotiation: skillful exchange of ideas, considerations, and compromises required when coordinating people's relations, solving conflicts, and attaining individual and collective objectives. In an academic setting especially in the state universities of the US, negotiation skills influence various forms of the organizational operations such as faculty hire, budgeting, curriculum and program development and initiative with other institutions among others.

The purpose of this paper is to examine the role of negotiation skills in employability and organisational performance with reference to Sri Lankan state universities. Sri Lanka has a young and fast growing HE sector and the current environment is complex with much potential for change

where effective negotiation is crucial. It is therefore the intention of this research to first explore negotiation skills among university professionals while secondly exploring how such skills play out in relation to promotion and or advancement and consequently the role they play in the realisation of institutional objectives. In addition, the study aims to give insights on the ‘call’ for training and development efforts that enhance negotiation competence which will be of ample and useful advantage not only to the individuals but to the academic society in Sri Lanka as well.

Despite the importance of negotiation, little attention has been given to how well faculty and administrative staff in Sri Lankan universities develop and use these skills to advance their careers and enhance organizational effectiveness. This research aims to fill that gap by examining how negotiation impacts these areas.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

To analyze the importance of negotiation skills for career development in Sri Lanka's state universities.

To assess the role of negotiation in organizational effectiveness, particularly in resource allocation, conflict resolution, and decision-making.

To propose recommendations for improving negotiation training for academic and administrative staff.

1.4 Research Questions

How do negotiation skills influence career development in Sri Lanka's state universities?

What is the impact of negotiation on organizational effectiveness, particularly in resource management and conflict resolution?

What strategies can enhance negotiation skills among university employees?

2. Literature Review

2.1 The Concept of Negotiation

In its broad standpoint, negotiation refers to the act taken by the two or more individuals in an attempt to attain his/her/their goals while the counterpart does the same. It incorporates the activities of reaching out, confrontation and compromise, and systematic choice and plans (Fisher & Ury, 1981).

2.2 Negotiation Skills in Career Development

Babcock and Laschever (2003) Week 1 note that people who know how to negotiate benefits have better chances of receiving such aspects as promotion, an increase in pay, and other better working conditions. In academic career these skills are essential in obtaining research grants, negotiating for teaching and other related assignments and getting tenure.

2.3 Negotiation Effectiveness and Organisation

Lewicki et al. (2015) defined negotiation vital in organizational achievement since it is applied in various capacities including managing of conflict, sharing of rewards, and developing strong working relationships between departments. In universities, this involves managing distribution of resources, management of academic work and solving conflicts between faculty and authorities.

2.4 The Sri Lankan Context

The environment in which state universities in Sri Lanka function is extremely formalised and bureaucratic. This has implications on the complexity of negotiation processes especially with regard to distribution of resources as well as decision making (Perera & Jayasekara, 2020). The organisation structure of the university in Sri Lanka is more in a hierarchical manner, where it can

be said that depending on the skills for the negotiation among the parties, it can prove to be a boon or bane.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This research employs both qualitative interviews and quantitative questionnaires. Participants of the study consist of faculty and administrative staff in three major state university in Sri Lanka. These included face-to-face interviews with formulated questions and survey questionnaire used to assess negotiation skills and how they affect the respondent's and organization's career advancement and efficiency.

3.2 Sampling

For the purpose of achieving cross-sectional representation, a stratified sampling method was used. This study sample consists of 50 faculty members including teachers and lecturers from the University of Colombo, University of Peradeniya, and University of Kelaniya, 20 administrative staff.

3.3 Data Collection

The survey instrument used Likert-scale questions to assess negotiation skills in five key areas: minded; conflict solving; salary discussion; points distribution; verbal interaction; supervision. The authors also interviewed nine department heads and senior administrative officers using framed questions in semi-structured interviews to get more nuanced views of negotiation in the university system.

3.4 Data Analysis

Descriptive analysis and regression analysis tests involving mathematical computations were employed to relate skill domain in negotiation and career progression. Interview data were content analyzed to categorize insights into descriptors and subgroups to look for patterns.

4. Discussion

4.1 The Role of Negotiation in Career Development

Results indicate a strong correlation between negotiation skills and career progression in Sri Lankan state universities. Faculty members who actively engaged in salary and resource negotiations were more likely to receive promotions and secure research grants. Negotiation was also a significant factor in managing workloads and obtaining teaching reliefs for research activities.

It is especially important skill in career advancement because it determines an employee's progress with respect to promotions, remuneration, relations with managers and colleagues, and organisational commitment. Negotiation skills help professionals gain insight in expressing themselves professionally and gaining leverage over instances which prevail in organizations. The role of negotiation in career development can be seen in several key areas:

Salary and benefits bargaining is possibly the most straightforward manner by which negotiation influences career growth. In achieving fairness of remunerations; workers lay a platform on which succeeding promotions and or salary hikes are normally built. These findings suggest that salary bargaining by employees can potentially alter pay levels that accumulate over the long haul and produce major financial and career returns (Ahamed et al, 2018).

Promotion as well as changing positions within an organization require bargaining skills. Readers have to be informed about accomplishments, how the professional can help more, and it is necessary to promote the new tasks. Negotiation for various career progression is not only

beneficial in attaining promotion, but it powers one's profile within the company to earn a reputation for assuming leadership in various events that seek promotion.

Conflict isn't solely about getting things done for the better, especially where power relations and cooperation are required. Workers who successfully negotiate are well aware of the role of compassion, attentiveness and cooperation. Building and sustaining rapport with other co-workers, tutors as well as managers is crucial while in the course of advancing one's career. Negotiation strengthens the relationship between team members and brings about respect fostering organizational cooperation and also creates employment openings in the future based on the good working relationship (Siraju, M et al, 2023).

Introducing that conflict is in one's workplace, depends on how the conflict is handled then affects one respectively in his/ her profession. People who are equipped with high degree of negotiation competency are regarded as solvers of conflicts who are well equipped to handle issues pertaining to conflict with a lot of ease. This capability is useful for self-advancement because organizations always prefer employees who can manage situations and conflicts in ways that contribute to productivity in workplace.

4.2 Negotiation and Organizational Effectiveness

Negotiation skills played a vital role in organizational effectiveness, particularly in resource allocation. Departments with heads proficient in negotiation were better at securing funding and balancing departmental needs. Conflict resolution, another important area of negotiation, was found to reduce tensions between faculty members and the administration, leading to improved organizational climate.

4.3 Challenges in Developing Negotiation Skills

Nonetheless, although negotiation seems to be a crucial interpersonal skill for health care staff members, educational preparation in this expected competency was found to be limited. Overall, the analysis has shown that there is a huge chasm between recommended and existing negotiation capabilities of the people at Arcadia University especially but not solely the junior faculty and administrative employees. Surprisingly, in many universities negotiation initiatives are not institutionalised and policy makers rely on apprenticeship.

4.4 Social Power Dynamics of Hierarchy

Relationship power dynamics are another constraint – Sri Lankan universities are particularly hierarchical. Starting employees experience challenges in bargaining with the managers or elderly professors, and this is attributed to culture that frowns upon the staff to counter the seniors. These structural barriers hamper intergroup communication and sharing of resources and services hence reducing organizational adaptability.

5. Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

The current study indicates that, negotiation skills are imperative in career progression and organizational performance for Sri Lankan state universities. The study is able to support the idea that those who have good negotiation skills are likely to get promotions, reduce workloads and make inputs for the efficiency of the departments. Nevertheless, there is ample evidence of a trend that requires significant improvements in the current formal negotiation training system.

5.2 Recommendations

Training Programs: It would be beneficial for universities to have an organized negotiation training for their faculty and their administrative employees. These can be applied in skill development fora or leadership seminar/training.

Mentorship Initiatives: One way of getting around this problem is to assign junior staff members to senior staff members who are good negotiators, which would foster negotiation in departments.

Policy Reforms: University management teams should review their policies on speaking out concerning bargaining issues with employers for a change with reference to workload and resources distribution.

Cultural Shifts: It can be also concluded that eliminating the hierarchical barriers in Universities is about creating the equal communication context, in which all employees would be able to negotiate for what they need.

REFERENCES

1. Babcock, L., & Laschever, S. (2003). *Women Don't Ask: Negotiation and the Gender Divide*. Princeton University Press.
2. Fisher, R., & Ury, W. (1981). *Getting to Yes: Negotiating Agreement Without Giving In*. Penguin Books.
3. Lewicki, R. J., Saunders, D. M., & Barry, B. (2015). *Negotiation*. McGraw-Hill.
4. Perera, M., & Jayasekara, S. (2020). "Challenges in Higher Education Management in Sri Lanka: A Case Study of Public Universities". *Journal of Educational Management*, 32(4), 143-157.
5. De Dreu, C. K. (1997). *Productive Conflict: Managing Disagreement in Organizations*. Sage Publications.
6. Siraju, M., Marsook, M., & Rifky, M. (2023). A comprehensive theoretical evaluation of the university grants commission (ugc) admission policy for undergraduate programs in sri lanka. *Прикладные науки в современном мире: проблемы и решения*, 2(11), 4-9.
7. Ahamed, S. T., Niyas, P. M., & Rifky, A. L. M. (2018). Identify the significance of performance appraisals on employee work improvement in software development organizations. *Int. J. Sci. Res. Publ*, 8(4), 399-404.